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Rapid Transit Oriented Morphological Transformations in Indian Cities: A Case of Kolkata Metro

Tazyeen Alam, and Ankhi Banerjee

Abstract

TOD (Transit-Oriented Development) is a long-term development strategy to increase metropolitan regions' quality of life (QoL). The Metro Rail Transit System (MRTS) is an integral part of the TOD plan and significantly impacts contemporary urban development. It is a crucial transformation parameter that influences the overall urban structure. Kolkata was the first Indian city to undergo the TOD urban transformation.

The paper examines the historical context of MRTS in the KMC region using conceptual, metric, and non-metric data analysis. This study aims to look at the altering urban morphology within a 400-800 m influence zone of two metro stations in Kolkata Municipal Corporation (KMC). The first is an old metro precinct in Kalighat (operational since 1986), while the second is a new metro precinct in Kavi Nazrul (operational since 1986) that is a newly developed area. Under TOD rules, both stations precincts are examined based on built-up area typologies, the ratio of green spaces, change in existing water bodies, typical traffic, and corresponding land values. Since 1991, the Kalighat metro station precinct has had a dense built up area (BUA) with little change in the urban form, thereby abiding by the TOD policies. The Kavi Nazrul metro station precinct has seen a significant expansion in the BUA due to metro arrival and related services in 2009. Still, it is under development and has not reached the threshold set by TOD policies in the current scenario. Therefore, the study will be helpful for planners and policy makers to plan for a more efficient QoL.

Keywords: Land-Use, Metro Rail Transit System, Transit-Oriented Development, Urban Form, Urban Morphology

1.0 INTRODUCTION

TOD promotes the integration of designed urban areas and people and urban activities, buildings, and other public spaces by facilitating walkability and connectivity between different parts of a city. It delivers local and city-level accessibility through efficient and healthful means of transportation. Compact, walkable, pedestrian-oriented non-motorized transit (NMT) and mixed-use development with high-quality public transit are encouraged in a futuristic approach for sustainability, equity, vitality, and livability within an urban region. As a result, it lowers people's stress levels and lessens their reliance on private vehicles.

TOD contributes to enhancing residential, commercial, and leisure spaces in urban areas, resulting in more interconnected urban environments. In most TODs, the transit corridor is a mixed-use corridor with peak-hour traffic on both sides and directions. As a result, a TOD makes it possible to meet the basic demands of everyday travel to work and recreation without using your vehicle. TOD also encourages job concentration and densification in limited locations. As a result, an agglomeration effect occurs, improving the metropolitan area's competitiveness. Previous research has shown that TOD doubles job density, resulting in a 5% to 10% increase in regional economic production. The increased productivity results from luring activity to the main transportation stations, which contributes to the idea of living and walkable communities.

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Fig. 1: TOD along with Transit Stations (National Urban Transport Policy)

Source: MOHUA (2019)

Table 1: Definitions of Transit-Oriented Development (TOD)

Authors	Definition
Calthorpe (1993)	Mixed-use community within an average 2,000 ft walking distance of a transit stop and a core commercial area that mixes residential, retail, office, open space, and public uses in a walkable environment, making it convenient for residents and employees to travel by transit, bicycle, foot, or car.
Bernich and Cervero (1997)	A compact, mixed-use community centred on a transit station that, by design, invites residents, workers, and shoppers to drive their cars less and ride mass transit more.
Stil (2003)	A mixed-use community encourages people to live near transit services and decreases their dependence on driving.
Cervero et al. (2004)	TOD is a tool for promoting smart growth, leveraging economic development, and catering for shifting housing market demands and lifestyle preferences.
Maryland Department of Transportation	A place of relatively higher density that includes a mixture of residential, employment, shopping and civic uses and types located within an easy walk of bus or rail transit centre.

TOD is inextricably linked to the MRTS (Mass Rapid Transit System). It plays an essential role in providing individuals with first- and last-mile connections. It contributes to creating a congestion-free zone around the transit station, allowing for smooth traffic flow. The decision to use MRTS as a TOD is influenced by a number of criteria, including demand, capacity, ease of implementation, and cost. The ability of the MRTS is generally defined by the passengers per hour per direction (PPHPD). A metro rail can transport many passengers each hour (about 60,000 to 80,000 PPHPD), ensuring regular, high-quality, and speedy service in urban areas.

One of the most essential takeaways from the TOD assessment is that a TOD often allows for a dense, mixed-use development built around transit stations. It is more than just a planning approach; it supports transportation stations and benefits from closeness. As a result, its primary goal is to reduce car use by shortening trips and encouraging the use of MRTS and other sustainable forms of last-mile connection, such as walking, cycling, and other NMT. The proximity of the transit station, mixed land use, density levels, accessibility to walking and utilizing NMT, principal transport mode, availability of public spaces, and the impact of reducing automobile usage are all factors that influence TOD. As a result, the influence areas

of TOD are defined as “areas polarized by a centre for a set of relations (influence area of the city) or a category of connections (many areas including commercial and trading)” (Ann et al., 2019).

TOD Policies (MoHUA):

To satisfy the growing travel demand as cities grow, transportation systems such as metro rail, BRTS, and others are being implemented. As a result, TOD has become an unavoidable requirement for all cities with existing or planned public transit systems. The state government is responsible for managing urban spaces; nevertheless, a national TOD strategy would serve as a framework and catalyst for developing state / city laws that promote transit-oriented development. The vision of the policy is threefold - Enable Transformation, Accessible Public Transport, and Compact Walkable Communities. To fulfil the various objectives, TOD integrates land use and transportation planning to construct compact growth centres within the influence zone of 500-800 metres on either side of transit stations, i.e. regions within walking distance. The major policies related to the study include walkable distance to transit stations within 500-800 metres, mixed land use and high rise development within this influence zone.

Fig. 2: Components of TOD

Source: National Urban Transport Policy, MOHUA (2016)

- TOD promotes the growth and development of transportation planning and land use on both sides of transit stations within 500 to 800 metres, or 10 to 12 minutes walking distance. The influence zones try to limit private vehicle consumption and mixed land use development.
- A mix of land uses near transportation stations helps optimize the physical infrastructure with all available resources while keeping the area active because these services operate during the day.
- TOD also places restrictions on some types of construction, such as low-density housing and low-rise development, to allow for the most activity in the influence zones. Limiting warehouses / factories, cremation grounds, petrol pumps, and multilevel or surface parking to offer more space for hassle-free traffic flow and other needed tasks is also part of the plan.
- The TOD policies recommend that horizontal or vertical operations in the influence zone achieve mixed-use. Vertical mixing would combine multiple activities in the same building, whereas horizontal mixing would include different activities in separate buildings. Housing in the influence zone must cater to all socioeconomic groups. All persons who rely on public transportation should have the same opportunity to reside near a transit station.

TOD emphasizes first- and last-mile connection, resulting in more excellent non-motorized transportation (NMT) usage outside the influence zone.

2.0 MRTS IN KOLKATA MUNICIPAL CORPORATION (KMC)

Metro connection is a method of expanding accessibility that has been in use since the early 1960s worldwide. The first metro line in India was built in Kolkata in October 1984 and was finished in 1995, followed by the Delhi Metro in 2002. Kolkata's metro system has a total length of 28.14 kilometers, with another 63.39 kilometers under construction. The development of the metro system has revolutionized Kolkata's urban structure and economic potential. This influence is governed by two major factors: construction potentials and job potentials.

Fig. 3: Delineation of Metro Route through KMC

Source: Author (2021)

Kolkata's metro system began with a line from Esplanade to Netaji Bhavan and was later extended to Dum Dum in the north. The electric current was used to access the first Metro, built underground. Since 1995, the later additions have been motorized. The MRTS served most of the ancient city centre and improved connectivity to the outlying populace through the KMC area. The Kolkata Metro Rail Corporation (KMRC) built and maintained all metro lines. Extensions to the south (Kavi Subhash in 2010) and north (Kavi Subhash in 2011) were among the subsequent expansions to the same line (Noapara in 2013). The former connects significant metropolitan stretches in the central metropolis, while the latter is associated with the expansion axis.

Fig. 4: Kolkata Metro Timeline Flowchart

Source: Author (2021)

Kolkata and Howrah were among the cities that sprung up on both sides of the Hooghly River. As a result, the new metro line will connect these two key hubs. This research examines the predicted changes in the KMC area’s urban structure due to the MRTS. To comprehend the morphological changes in the KMC area, the study undertakes a critical assessment of the present urban form and land use. Two transit stations, Kalighat (old) and Kavi Nazrul, are among the research focal locations (new). The Kalighat metro station, which dates back to 1986, is part of the first metro line. The Kavi Nazrul metro station, an extension of the existing metro line, has been operational since 2009 (Figure). KMC owns a large portion of the impact zone surrounding the Kavi Nazrul metro station, while

Rajpur-Sonarpur Municipality owns the rest (RSM).

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The TOD strategy considerably impacts Kolkata’s land use and urban layout. The regions around the new Metro lines are expected to undergo a similar transformation. This article aims to compare and forecast changes in the urban morphology of the influence zone along the existing metro route in the Kolkata Metropolitan Corporation (KMC) area. The study’s goal is to determine how MRTS affects the urban form of the Kalighat and Kavi Nazrul metro station influence zones. The study uses conceptual, metric, and non-metric data analysis to assess the historical backdrop of MRTS in the KMC area. It was carried out at a detailed level within 500 m of the metro precinct and a broader level within 2000 m. The research used a qualitative analysis and reconnaissance survey approach to explore the many views connected to changes in urban morphology. The study utilizes urban morphological parameters for study - population density, BUA, and building heights. The study areas’ BUA, typical traffic, node density, and land-use changes were analyzed to understand the overall shift in urban morphology better. Images from the Landsat 8 Thematic Map (LTM) between 2000 and 2020 were used to evaluate urban spatial trends.

4.0 ANALYSIS / DISCUSSION

The KMC area is the region’s primary urban agglomeration, with a current population of more than 4.5 million people living in 206.08 square kilometers and a population density of 24,252 people per square kilometer. The metropolis also accommodates a daily population

of 60,00,000 people (KMC, 2019). Between 1981 and 1991, the trend of urban growth in KMC accelerated due to migration from neighboring areas searching for work in the central city. KMC grew along a straight line till 2001. Between 2001 and 2011, population growth slowed by 1.8 per cent, according to Census 2011. The population of KMC is estimated to reach 4.55 million in 2021, an increase of 1.18 per cent since 2011. As a result, Kolkata is no longer the fastest-growing metropolis in West Bengal, and population growth patterns imply that the city has reached a saturation point (Author, 2021). The city grew less crowded during the population fall, and new inhabitants relocated to the suburbs.

Table 2: Primary Land Use share in the Wards of KMC - Kalighat and Kavi Nazrul Metro Station Areas

Metro Station	Ward No.	Land use share within the influence zone of 400 m	TOD policies
Kalighat	83	75% residential 25% mixed-use Very less pure commercial	The TOD policy of mixed land use is satisfied.
	84	20% pure commercial Remaining majorly residential mixed-use	
	87	Majorly residential	
	88	25% mixed-use Rest is mainly residential	
Kavi Nazrul	100	Majorly residential	Mostly residential
	110	20% mixed-use	With small
	111	Majorly residential	Percentage of mixed land use. Thus, TOD policy not satisfied.

Source: Bhuvan (2016)

In the previous decade, the population and population density of South Kolkata has increased, notably since the MRTS was extended across Tolly's Nullah. Both metro stations, Kalighat and Kavi Nazrul, are located in South Kolkata (Table). Since 1984, the Kalighat Metro station has been located on Shyama Prasad Mukherjee Road. It helped the area's economic development and raised the standard of living, hence improving QoL. Because of the facilities and opportunities provided by the MRTS, more people decided to reside along the section of Tolly's Nullah in later years. As a result, it was easier for people, schools, institutions, offices, and commercial locations to communicate with a larger audience more quickly. KMC ward numbers 83, 84, 87, and 88 make up the site area (500 m × 500 m). According to the district planning map of Kolkata (NATMO), the land use is primarily residential, with road peripheries being mixed-use residential and commercial. Greenspace accounts for 5% of the total area, with a small amount serving as a public or semi-public space for the Kalighat temple complex.

There was an increase in population and population density of South Kolkata in the last decade, especially after the extension of MRTS across Tolly's Nullah. The Kalighat and Kavi Nazrul, both metro stations, are located in South Kolkata. The Kalighat Metro station has been located at Shyama Prasad Mukherjee Road since 1984. It contributed to the economic enhancement of the area and improved the standard of living and hence the QoL. In the later years, more people chose to recite along the stretch of Tolly's Nullah due to the facilities and opportunities offered by the MRTS. Therefore, it was convenient for the people and the schools, colleges, offices and commercial areas to connect with the distant audience more rapidly. The site area (500m x

Fig. 5: District Planning Land Use Map to Study the two Metro Stations within KMC (A- Kalighat Metro Station, and B- Kavi Nazrul Metro Station), and Compare a Non-Metro Area (C- Diamond Harbour Road, Kidderpore)

Source: NATMO (2019)

500 m) consists of KMC ward numbers 83, 84, 87 and 88. As per the district planning map of Kolkata (NATMO), the Land-use is majorly residential with road peripheries as mixed-use residential and commercial. The green spaces are 5 per cent, and a small portion is designated as public or semi-public space for the Kalighat temple complex.

Since 2009, the Kavi Nazrul Metro station has been located on Nayabad Main Road. It is being developed and consists of elderly citizens who are either illiterate or have only received primary school. The location includes KMC wards 100, 110, and 111 and Rajpur-Sonarpur Municipality ward 24. Within the KMC limit, most of the land is used for residential purposes, with allotted space for state transportation depots and commercial sectors. A minor fraction includes mixed-use residential and retail industries and 10% green space. From 2000 to 2020, a comparative analysis of metro stations estimates the physical structure, open and green areas, water bodies, and usual traffic. It aids in comprehending changes in the morphological components of urban regions in both metro precincts and suburban locations.

Built-Up Area (BUA):

According to the 2001 Census data, the wards of the Kalighat site area have a total population of 88,155 people. The BUA (Built-Up Area) accounts for around 95.13 per cent of the entire area of 1.93 square kilometers. According to the Census 2011 data, the wards have more than 77,740 people, with a BUA of about 96.84 per cent. Between 2000 and 2020, the population and BUA increased. (Figure (a)). The site had a fine-grain urban shape in 2001, with a population density of 45676.17 ppsq km. By 2020, it had become coarse-grained, with a 40279.79 pp sq km population density.

Fig. 6: Kalighat Metro Station Precinct and Influence Areas of 400 m and 800 m

Source: Author (2021)

Due to the restricted space available in the metro precinct, the urban expansion was vertical, with buildings being raised in height to accommodate more people in the same area. As a result, in 2000, the buildings in the metro precinct were low-rise high-density, but by 2020, they had evolved to high-rise, high-density mixed land use along Shyama Prasad Mukherjee road. The Kalighat metro station, which opened in 1991, was already surrounded by dense, low-rise development. The BUA gradually transitioned from low-rise medium-density construction to mid-rise high-density development. Due to site scarcity and historic building fabric, only a few high-rise developments are beyond the metro influence zone. However, on the Eastern side of the metro route, where Rashbehari Avenue and Hazra Road are located, a major development has happened in comparison to the other side.

$$\text{Building density within 400 m} = \frac{\text{Total number of units}}{\text{Total area}} = \frac{3069}{0.20} = 19,820 \text{ units / sq km}$$

The right hand side of the Kalighat metro is developed on the basis of Kolkata's history of development and is therefore compact in nature. The left hand side of the metro is a part of Kolkata and developed due to various other reasons which is not within the scope of this study.

The Kavi Nazrul site area wards have a population of more than 84,579 persons, according to the 2001 Census data. The BUA (Built-Up Area) covers approximately 9.32% of the total 6.34 square kilometers. The wards have a total population of more than 91,624 individuals, with a BUA of roughly 57.76 per cent, according to Census 2011 data. Between 2000 and 2020, the number of people and BUA increased (Figure 7(b)). The site had a fine-grain urban shape in

Fig. 7: Figure-ground Map for (a) Kalighat Metro Station Precinct, and (b) Kavi Nazrul Metro Station Precinct, for 500 m x 500 m Site Area

Source: Author (2021)

2001, with a population density of 13340.54 pp sq km. By 2020, it had become coarse-grained, with a population density of above 14451.74 pp sq km. Due to space constraints on the KMC's urban edges, the urban expansion was horizontal. As a result, in 2000, the buildings in the metro precinct were low-rise, low-density. Still, by 2020, they had evolved into mid-rise, mid-density mixed land use along the Pranabananda and Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose highways.

Table 3 shows that the Kalighat Metro precinct has had a high percentage of BUA since 1991, probably as a result of the Metro and its associated services. The BUA grew in Kavi Nazrul after the Metro was installed in 2009. There was a huge growth in BUA. Because there was no metro on Diamond Harbour Road in Kidderpore, the BUA was lower than in Kalighat. However, it was near to the Kolkata port. However, due to other development variables, the BUA rose over time.

Table 3: Percentage of BUA in Both the Metro Station Influence Zones (400 m) and Non Metro Location Near Diamond Harbour Road

Location	1991	2001	2011	2014
Kalighat metro precinct	94.32	95.13	96.84	97.83
Kavi Nazrul metro precinct	4.39	9.32	57.76	61.54
Diamond Harbour road, Kidderpore	63.73	86.04	93.96	96.03

Source: Author (2021)

$$\text{Building density within 400m} = \frac{\text{Total number of units}}{\text{Total area}} = \frac{3069}{0.20} = 15,345 \text{ units / sq km.}$$

Like any other urban edge, the Kavi Nazrul metro station location was not intensively developed and had large open areas in 1991. After 2001, significant progress was made. The populace began to settle in this part of the KMC region, primarily due to the planned metro extension in 2009. People flocked to the outskirts because the land prices were low. The upcoming Metro will bring a wide range of amenities and possibilities to the surrounding neighborhoods. As a result, a significant change occurred around 2009. The Kavi Nazrul metro station location still has room for future expansion. The present growth is a mid-rise, mid-density development. The proposed gated community concept does not adhere to TOD rules, which encourage housing for people from various walks of life. A gated community fosters the inclusion of just certain types of people. As a result, while comparing the KMC area of the precinct to the KMDA

Fig. 8: Kavi Nazrul Metro Station Precinct and Influence Areas of 400 m and 800 m

Source: Author (2021)

area (consisting of Rajpur-Sonarpur Municipality regions) inside the precinct, a considerable development in urban fabric was noticed. Male commuters outnumber female commuters in the Metro, with 65 percent of male commuters and 35 percent of female commuters. Approximately 60% of daily commuters are members of the working class, 30% are students of various age groups, and the remainder are women, housewives, children, retired people, and senior citizens (Kundu and Ray, 2014).

Open and Green Spaces:

According to the district land use map, both sites have fewer open and green areas. The area of open and green spaces visible on the figure-ground map and Landsat 8 Thematic Maps in 2000 was 6,163 sq m, or 2.54% of the Kalighat metro precinct site area. Green areas accounted for 2.37 per cent of the total site area in 2020, comprising 5,756 square metres. For expansion or renewal, the Shyama Prasad Mukherjee road structures overtake the allocated open and green spaces. As a result, the open and green spaces have decreased by 0.17 per cent overall (Figure 9 (a)). The area of open and green spaces seen from the figure-ground map and Landsat 8 Thematic Maps in 2000 was 13,159 sq.m, or 6.03 per cent of the total site area of the Kavi Nazrul metro precinct. By 2020, the open and green areas had shrunk to 5.40 per cent of the overall site area, covering 11,820 square metres. Buildings along the Nayabad main road overtake designated open and green spaces, primarily for

Fig. 9: Open and Green Area for (a) Kalighat Metro Station Precinct, and (b) Kavi Nazrul Metro Station Precinct, for 500 m x 500 m Site Area

Source: Author (2021)

recent construction. As a result, the open and green spaces have decreased by 0.63 per cent overall (Figure 9(b)).

Water Bodies:

For the Kalighat metro station precinct, the area of water bodies remains constant. Between 2000 and 2020, there was little change in the water bodies. The number of water bodies present is also insignificant (Figure 10(a)). The area of water bodies seen from the figure-ground map and Landsat 8 Thematic Maps in 2000 was 8,869 sq m, or 4.06 per cent of the total site area of the Kavi Nazrul metro precinct. Water bodies accounted for 2.43 per cent of the whole site surface in 2020, spanning 5,324 square metres. Since the start of the metro extension project, the width of Tolly’s Nullah has shrunk dramatically. Between 2000 and 2020, a few more water features within the Kavi Nazrul metro precinct site vanished. As a result, the water bodies have decreased by 1.63 per cent overall (Figure 10(b)).

Fig. 10: Water Bodies Map for (a) Kalighat Metro Station Precinct, and (b) Kavi Nazrul Metro Station Precinct, for 500 m x 500 m Site Area

Source: Author (2021)

Typical Traffic:

The collection of regular traffic data from Google Maps was supported by the GPS of persons in various areas. On Fridays between 10 am and 6 pm, the Kalighat metro station precinct witnessed considerably very high traffic within 400 metres of the transit station, primarily on the roads along the metro route. It had high to moderate traffic on Wednesdays at 1.30 pm during lunchtime. On Sunday nights at 10 pm, it had less traffic (Figure 11). According to usual traffic data, the Kavi Nazrul metro station precinct witnessed considerably high to moderate traffic within 400 metres of the transit station on Mondays at 10 am and Fridays at 6 pm. The roads along the metro route was subject to maximum traffic. On Fridays at 1.30 pm, it had controllable medium traffic, and on Mondays at 10 pm, it had minimal traffic. As a result,

Fig. 11: Typical Traffic Mapping for Kalighat Metro Station

Source: Author (2021)

traffic congestion at the transit station crossing in the Kalighat metro precinct is more severe, resulting in longer travel times.

During peak office hours, the Kavi Nazrul metro precinct encounters congestion at the vital road crossings, still developing its influence zone. On Fridays at 6 pm, however, both transit station precincts experience heavy traffic. On weekdays, from 9.30 am to 10 am, 1.30 pm, and 6 pm, there is typically considerable traffic in the influence zone of both metro stations, which then subsides. There is the least amount of traffic on weekends in both metro station influence zones (Figure 12).

Fig. 12: Typical Traffic Mapping for Kavi Nazrul Metro Station

Source: Author (2021)

As per the TOD guidelines, the metro should lead to increased use of Non-Motorized Vehicles (NMVs) within the influence zone. But in Kalighat, the regular traffic of motorized vehicles are considerably high. For both metro station precincts, the integration values from space syntax reveal a significant variance. The Kalighat metro precinct has the highest level of integration (connectivity), particularly in Kalighat and, to a lesser extent, at Jatin Das Park. Because of the increased integration of connections throughout the precinct, the orange to red transition inside the 400 m transition zone suggests that residents residing within this zone will be able to reach metro stations. Because the region around the Kavi Nazrul metro precinct is still expanding, there are high integration values immediately around the metro precinct, but these values quickly drop within the 400 m and increase within the 800 m zones. Thus, within the influence zones, Kalighat has much better connectivity as compared to Kavi Nazrul metro station precinct. Thus, it is more accessible than Kavi Nazrul despite of the high typical traffic.

Fig. 13: Connectivity within Influence Zones of 488-800 m in (a) Kalighat Metro Station Precinct, and (b) Kavi Nazrul Metro Station Precinct

Source: Author (2021)

The node density in traffic routes, which is expressed as an index or a percentage, is used to assess the accessibility of road networks. The higher the node density rating, the more roads that are connected. As a result, different routes are more accessible and available. As a result, the higher the node density, the less likely traffic congestion and smooth traffic flow will be possible. The network density between the nodes can define a node density. It depicts the prospective connections (PC) in a network by describing the current relationships (nodes) (AC). The potential connection is a link that could exist between two or more nodes even if they are not currently connected. Regardless of their potential, two or more nodes have an appropriate relationship.

$$\text{Potential Connections (PC)} = \frac{n \times (n-1)}{2} \text{ where } n \text{ is the number of nodes in a network}$$

$$\text{Network Density (ND)} = \frac{\text{Actual Connections (AC)}}{\text{Potential Connections (PC)}} \times 100 \%$$

$$\text{Average Node Density (\%)} = \frac{\sum \text{Total Node Density}}{\text{Number of Nodes}}$$

Fig. 14: Influence Zone Integration Module for Kalighat Metro Station Using Space Syntax and Node Density for 500 m x 500 m Grid

Source: Author (2021)

Fig. 15: Influence Zone Integration Module for Kavi Nazrul Metro Station Using Space Syntax and Node Density for 500 m x 500 m Grid

Source: Author (2021)

The most congested parts of the Kalighat metro station have a node density of 40 to 50%, indicating fewer alternative routes and more significant traffic conflicts during peak hours. With primary node densities of roughly 50%, practically all nodes on the arterial and sub-arterial roads at Kavi Nazrul metro station require more access roads and alternate routes. As a result of the heavy use of roads, traffic movement within both metro station influence zones is slow, as the number of cars on the streets has also increased in the last two decades (Figure). The flow of traffic on the roads continues to be problematic. The entire acreage allotted for roads in the KMC region is less than 6% of the overall land usage, although it should be at least 10% to 12% of the total land use (URDPFI, 2015).

Land Price:

The Figure 16 depicts the trend in land values at various sites within the metro station precincts. The value of the areas along the metro line’s path rises, while the value of the regions further away decreases. Following the same trend, the land value of the Kavi Nazrul Metro station precinct will be higher than the land value of Kalighat. The minimum land price in the Kalighat area is Rs. 7,200 / sq ft. The minimum land price in the Kavi Nazrul area is Rs. 1,800 / sq ft. As a result, the region needs more property for diverse purposes, principally residential and mixed-use residential and commercial. Horizontal development is limited in the Kalighat Metro metro station precinct and other earlier metro stations.

Fig. 16: Housing Affordability in 2021 along the Old Metro Route (Kalighat) within 10 km of Metro Line Precinct

Source: Compiled by Author from several websites including magicbricks, housing, makaan, and 99acres (2021)

In 2004-2005, land prices were from 1.5-3 lakh per *cutta*, but by August 2011, they had climbed to 7-15 lakh per *cutta*. The greatest price was found within a 1 km radius of the stations, and the price reduced as the distance from the station increased. The cost of an apartment has also risen significantly. In 2006-2007, it was Rs. 700-1300 / sq ft, while in 2011, it was Rs. 2500-3500 / sq ft.

Fig. 17: Housing Affordability in 2021 along the Old Metro Route (Kavi Nazrul) within 10 km of Metro Line Precinct

Source: Compiled by Author from several websites including magicbricks, housing, makaan, and 99acres (2021)

This significant spike in price might be attributed to the Metro Railway's excellent accessibility. It is one of the most desirable places to live because of the good accessibility given by the metro system over a large area. As a result, the number of residential structures has expanded (Kundu and Ray, 2014). In 2021 it is observed that the area of Kavi Nazrul station towards KMC has higher land prices as compared to areas towards KMDA. A significant increase in prices were observed after the introduction of metro. Therefore, the areas will be looking forward to more prices.

5.0 RESULTS

In both Kalighat and Kavi Nazrul, the Metro has had considerable influence. Precincts around metro stations are unique. The former is an older settlement, while the latter is a newer one. In both cases, accessibility from the city centre to the suburbs improved. It signals the start of KMC's future growth. The MRTS in the KMC region makes it easier for inhabitants to go around and encourage additional activities in and around the influence zone. It raises the region's value within 800 metres of the transit station and increases population density (Figure). Thus, a significant increase in land prices are also observed in the developing metro station precincts (Kavi Nazrul) while it is extremely high in case of old metro precincts (Kalighat). The area's regeneration favours enormous grain size growth with a high-rise and high density along important roadways like the Kalighat Metro station precinct, notably in the Kavi Nazrul Metro station precinct. It changes the way roads are connected, resulting in more traffic intersections and conflict points. The Kavi Nazrul area also contributes to higher land prices and demand. As a result, the metro precinct's open green spaces and water bodies are depleted as a result of the overall development. However, the development was more considerable on one side of the metro area in both cases. In Kalighat, there has been a lot of growth towards Rashbehari Avenue, however in Kavi Nazrul, the KMC area

has seen greater development than the KMDA of the precinct. Comparing the Kalighat Metro station area to another location in Kolkata with a comparable land use pattern, road network, the Metro has had a substantial impact on Kolkata's urban growth pattern in case of Kalighat area as compared to the other part of Diamond Harbour Road. The former metro line had a significant impact on the neighborhood. After 1984, the operational Metro causes a fast growth in the BUA. The other region does not have a metro line, although it is well connected to Diamond Harbour Road via road. The BUA has gradually expanded, although not in the same way as the Kalighat area. Therefore, the area will be looking forward to more prices.

6.0 CONCLUSIONS

The analysis has found that the urban transformations along metro route in Kalighat area follow the Indian TOD norms. The TOD policy recommends the construction of high-density, high-rise structures within the influence zone and the establishment of the Kalighat metro station precinct has fostered high-rise, high-density growth. The metro extension's suburban section, which includes the Kavi Nazrul, is undergoing high-density development, comparable to the Kalighat area. Open spaces, green spaces, and water bodies continue to be neglected and unprotected. As a result, between 2000 and 2020, they declined. As a result, it is critical to pay close attention to the 10% open areas and green spaces required by the TOD rules within the influence zone of each transit station. Encouragement of public places and sustainable forms of transportation, such as walking, is critical. It will also assist the traffic management within the influence zone, which is difficult to accommodate in the Kalighat area. There is no room for horizontal public space expansion within the influence zone. The opportunities and facilities provided by the metro system, on the other hand, increase land prices in and around the transit station precinct. As a result, there is an increasing demand for speedy land supply and high rise construction for everyday activities and residential use. The metro railway expansion has improved connectivity for residents in the south Kolkata region. One of the key reasons for the expanding urban sprawl in the extreme south of Kolkata is the good connection given by the metro railway.

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